

MAR2PROTECT

Preventing groundwater contamination related to global and climate change through a holistic approach based on managed aquifer recharge

Stay tuned and check out the project results!

The project

MAR2PROTECT will provide a holistic approach to prevent **groundwater** contamination from climate change impacts, through different innovative technologies.

The main idea consists in a tool supported by **Artificial Intelligence** that will receive real-time information from sensors placed in risk locations where the technologies will be implemented, among other vitally important information (innovative technologies, preferences of social agents, risk assessment...).

The tool is based on a new generation of **Managed Aquifer Recharge** approach to improve groundwater quality and quantity. The core of the innovative Managed Aquifer Recharge is the **M-AI-R Decision Support System** which will incorporate technological and societal engagement information using an Artificial Intelligence-based evaluation to improve groundwater quality.

To ensure a high replication potential, M-AI-R Decision Support System will collect information from 7 demo sites in 4 European countries and 2 in non-European countries.

Lima river estuary, Portugal

Extensive coastal aquifer. Salt intrusion & diffuse pollution. NBS using saltmarshes

Katwijk, Netherlands

Dunal aquifer, salt intrusion. MAR using surface water

Emilia-Romagna, Italy

Coastal aquifer. Salt intrusion & diffuse pollution. MAR using MWW

Frielas, Portugal

Coastal aquifer. Salt intrusion. MAR using MWW

Marbella, Spain

Coastal aquifer. Salt intrusion. MAR using GW from an upstream aquifer

Nabeul, Tunisia

Over-exploited coastal aquifer. Salt intrusion & diffuse pollution. MAR using MWW and surface water

Cape Flats, South Africa

Coastal aquifer. Salt intrusion & diffuse pollution. MAR using MWW

MWW: Municipal Waste Water
NBS: Natural Based Solutions

